

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

RES4LIVE Final video

Deliverable D7.6

WP7. Dissemination – Communication – Exploitation

Project title

RES4LIVE - Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Grant agreement: 101000785

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Prepared by: CETRI

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.	Deliverable D7.6 RES4LIVE Final video
Responsible Partner	CETRI
WP no. and title	7. Dissemination – Exploitation – Communication
Task no. and title	T.7.1: Dissemination and communication plan and activities
Version	1
Version Date	30/09/2024

Dissemination level	
X	PU = Public
	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals/ Document history

	Company/Institution
Author/s	CETRI
Task Leader	CETRI
WP Leader	CETRI

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ABBREVIATIONS

PVT: Photovoltaic thermal

RES: Renewable Energy Sources

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PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This report includes information on the RES4LIVE final video developed under Task 7.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities, led by CETRI. The final RES4LIVE video presents the project's results and main achievements.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document is linked with Deliverable 7.6 “RES4LIVE Final video” and includes the final video produced at M48. The video was developed by CETRI, responsible for the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities during the project. The video presents the assistant coordinator, Mr. Dimitrios Tyriss, talking about the project and videos and images of the technological installations in the partner farms. The main objective of the video is to highlight the project’s activities and the impact that those technological achievements can have on the de-fossilization of livestock farming. The narration during the presentation of the technological installations is conducted by Mr. Tyriss. The video includes also English subtitles. The RES4LIVE final video has been uploaded to the YouTube account of the project.

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2 THE RES4LIVE FINAL VIDEO

2.1 The concept

The final RES4LIVE video was produced with the vision to describe all the achievements the consortium has made and the overall outcomes that were achieved. All partners provided the corresponding input on the project's technical results. The description is made by the assistant coordinator Mr. Dimitrios Tyris in popularized language to be addressed to a larger number of stakeholders and a broadened audience. The final video has a 3.30-minute duration.

2.2 Footage

The Consortium provided relevant footage to CETRI, depicting their work, including short clips and images from the RES installations and results. The video starts with the assistant coordinator Mr. Dimitrios Tyris talking about RES4LIVE and its objectives.

Figure 1. Mr. Tyris talks about RES4LIVE at the start of the final video.

Then, Mr. Tyris describes the technological RES installations on the four partner farms, i.e., ILVO swine farm, GOLINELLI swine farm, LVAT dairy farm and AUA poultry farm. While narrating, the video shows clips and images from those RES installations.

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Figure 2. Snapshot from the RES4LIVE final video showing the PVT installation at ILVO swine farm, Belgium.

Figure 3. Snapshot from the RES4LIVE final video showing the geothermal energy storage installation at GOLINELLI swine farm, Italy.

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Figure 4. Snapshot from the RES4LIVE final video showing the retrofitted tractor and the BioCNG station at LVAT dairy farm, Germany.

Figure 5. Figure 4. Snapshot from the RES4LIVE final video showing the LED lighting installation and smart controllers at AUA poultry farm, Greece.

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After that, Mr. Tyris concludes about the RES4LIVE technological achievements and the serving of the goals set at the beginning of the project and a final snapshot shows the RES4LIVE webpage and social media information, for the audience that would like to know more about the project.

The language of the video is rather plain to be understandable by a broader audience. The narration during the showing of RES installations is being conducted by Mr. Tyris. Throughout the entire video light music sounds in the background to make the video watching more pleasant for the audience. All video was edited by CETRI.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, the RES4LIVE final video development is described. The video was produced by CETRI, with the association of all project partners. The final RES4LIVE video targets the scientific and farming community as well as the broader public. The video is included in RES4LIVE's YouTube channel, as well as in RES4LIVE's website and social media accounts.